

Report on Scientific Cooperation within the Arctic: Understanding the Bottlenecks in Cross-Border Research

Josie Ward¹, Kirsi Latola^{2*} and Daria Vlasova³

¹University of the Faroe Islands and University of the Arctic

²Thule Institute, University of Oulu, Finland and University of the Arctic

³Northern Arctic Federal University and University of the Arctic, the Russian Federation

*Contact person: kirsi.latola@uarctic.org

Photo credit: Hannele Savela

The International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) is a non-governmental, international scientific organization. IASC pursues a mission of encouraging and facilitating cooperation in all aspects of Arctic research, in all countries engaged in Arctic research and in all areas of the Arctic region. IASC promotes and supports leading-edge interdisciplinary research in order to foster a greater scientific understanding of the Arctic region and its role in the Earth system. To translate research to policy, IASC also serves as an Observer to the Arctic Council and an affiliate of the International Science Council, oversees the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks, and leads the International Conference on Arctic Research Planning and other Arctic science assessments.

International Arctic Social Science Association (IASSA), established in 1990, is a professional association of social scientists and humanities scholars who work in the Arctic that encompasses disciplines relating to behavioral, psychological, cultural, anthropological, archaeological, linguistic, historical, social, legal, economic, environmental, and political subjects, as well as health, education, the arts and humanities, and related subjects. IASSA is an Observer to the Arctic Council and a member of the International Science Council.

The University of the Arctic (UArctic) is a cooperative network of universities, colleges, research institutes, and other organizations concerned with education and research in and about the North. UArctic builds and strengthens collective resources and collaborative infrastructure that enables member institutions to better serve their constituents and their regions. Through cooperation in education, research and outreach we enhance human capacity in the North, promote viable communities and sustainable economies, and forge global partnerships.

Acknowledgments

The survey was shared widely through a cooperation with the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) and the International Arctic Social Science Association (IASSA), which was a key element in getting valuable responses to the survey. The survey was also shared in various states, which is highly appreciated. Special thanks to the University of Arctic Research Office at Northern Arctic Federal University in Arkhangelsk, Russian Federation for translating and conducting the survey in Russian. The survey and report were reviewed by UArctic President Lars Kullerud and Vice-President Research Arja Rautio, both of whom are thanked for their assistance. IASC Executive secretary Allen Pope and President of IASSA Andrey Petrov are thanked for their input and valuable comments. Finally, all survey participants are thanked for their important input.

Summary

In May of 2017, the Ministers of Foreign Affairs for each of the eight Arctic states (Canada, Kingdom of Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, the Russian Federation, Sweden, USA) signed the “Agreement on Enhancing International Arctic Scientific Cooperation”. The goal of the Agreement is to increase cooperation and access among the Arctic countries, by providing better access to infrastructures, research areas, facilities and data. The overall prediction of the Agreement is that increased scientific cooperation in the Arctic will lead to greater development of scientific knowledge across the region. This report outlines the results from a survey conducted by University of the Arctic, in cooperation with IASC and IASSA, in the spring of 2019. The survey focused on understanding bottlenecks and positive practices in scientific cooperation and access across the Arctic. While some issues were presented, the results were overwhelmingly positive, with only 8% of 136 respondents having been denied access. These respondents mostly cited issues accessing data from other countries. There were also 64 cited accounts of positive cooperation from respondents. These encompassed a variety of experiences primarily research cooperation and educational activities based on the existing partnership and collaboration. The nationality of the respondents is diverse, with representation from all eight Arctic states and from a variety of non-Arctic states.

Background

The Agreement on Enhancing Arctic Scientific Cooperation (Appendix 1) was signed in May 2017 after which it has been ratified by all Arctic eight countries (Canada, Kingdom of Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, the Russian Federation, Sweden, USA). The purpose of the Agreement is to enhance cooperation in scientific activities in order to increase effectiveness and efficiency in the development of scientific knowledge about the Arctic. The key elements of enhanced cooperation are better access to research areas, infrastructures, facilities and data including education, training and entries and exits of the persons. The Agreement also highlights the inclusion of the Indigenous, Traditional and Local Knowledge, whose importance has recently been recognized by the Arctic Science Ministers in their joint statements in 2016 and 2018. The Third International Conference on Arctic Research Planning (ICARP III; <https://icarp.iasc.info/>) gathered scientists together to form a joint statement highlighting the need for more effective use of Indigenous, Traditional and Local Knowledge by engaging Northern and Indigenous communities and involving local, regional and global stakeholders in the co-design of sustained observation systems and models to help define mitigation and adaptation strategies. ICARP III further states that Arctic science should promote collaboration across disciplines and must be communicated beyond the Arctic research community and related institutions in order to reach key stakeholders, decision-makers, the future workforce and the general public.

This survey was conducted by the University of the Arctic (UArctic), which is an observer for Arctic Council, and together with International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) and International Arctic Social Sciences Association (IASSA) represent research and education in the circumpolar Arctic and beyond. With extensive membership and over 50 Thematic Networks focusing on Arctic research

and cooperation in all Arctic eight countries and in non-Arctic countries provided a good platform for conducting the survey on the bottlenecks in relation to scientific accessibility in the Arctic.

Goal and Objectives of the Survey

The Agreement has been in force since May of 2018 and for effective implementation it is important to know what the needs and problems faced by researchers and students in getting access to Arctic (nationally and internationally). The Kingdom of Denmark has the responsibility for coordinating the Agreement's implementation and reviewing its progress. A follow-up meeting was held in March 2019 in Helsinki to gather signatory parties and others to share their thoughts on the Agreement and its implementation and to discuss ways forward. For that meeting, an online survey was developed and shared by UArctic to find out the possible bottle necks in getting an access to Arctic sites and regions. The survey included a section of general questions on respondents' knowledge about the Agreement and its articles as well as the relevance of the Agreement to their research and work. The preliminary results, those collected by Feb 28th, 2019, were presented at the meeting in Helsinki in March. After that, the survey was re-announced jointly with IASC and IASSA and kept open until the end of April 2019, which proved to be a good decision to gather more answers and wider geographical reach.

Methodology

An open online survey was conducted via Webropol 2.0 version in February 12 – April 30 (Appendix 2). The survey was open to anyone interested and was promoted widely by social media (Twitter and Facebook), email newsletters and personal emails and websites, particularly on the UArctic, IASC, IASSA websites. The language of the survey was English and to increase participation in the Russian Federation, the survey was translated into Russian and sent out via email to Russian organizations and members of UArctic. This was organized and conducted by the UArctic Research Office located at the Northern Arctic Federal University in Arkhangelsk, the Russian Federation. Collected responses were then translated into English and sent to the UArctic Thematic Networks and Research Liaison Office at the University of Oulu in Finland, which organized and collected answers from the online survey. The answers received from the Russian Federation were compiled with the online survey results into one dataset. No personal data has been published or shared and only the issues provided have been presented.

The survey consisted of three parts: Contact information with the possibility to remain anonymous, A. Need and awareness of the Agreement, B. Examples of problems where the Agreement could be helpful in the future. The last section included open-ended questions on both the problems in obtaining access and best practices on successful cooperation and experiences. In the case of the Russian questionnaire, the background information and all questions were the same as the English survey, and the questionnaire form looked the same as the pdf from the online survey. All questions were compulsory to answer and in case of yes or no answers, there was always an N/A choice for those who didn't know how to answer or who preferred not to give an answer.

The survey answers were looked at as total percentages of all responses and at the country and region levels. At the country and regional level non-Arctic countries were pooled together due to small number of answers per country. In case of Norway, only one answer was received and therefore Norway is not included to the country-based figures. The number of responses per country varied a lot and therefore the survey was not treated as a scientific data.

Results

Geographical Distribution of the Respondents

The total number of respondents to the online survey was 112 from 17 countries in North America, Europe (incl. Greenland), the Russian Federation, and Asia, and 24 answers were received via email from the Russian Federation bringing total number of answers to 136 (Figure 1). From those who left their contact information, 66% represented universities and other higher educational institutions, 21% research institutions and 12% governmental or other organizations.

A majority of respondents (65%) answered on their own behalf, 20% for their research group, and 17% for their department or institution in general (Figure 2). 63% of the respondents stated that they knew about the Agreement when answering the survey, leaving 37% respondents who didn't know about the Agreement beforehand. When asked if respondents have a partner or collaborator in other country where they would like to have access, 77% answered yes. This shows that the survey was answered mostly by those who work and collaborate internationally.

Figure 1. Number of respondents by nationality (n=136).

Figure 2. The proportion of the persons answering for their own behalf, for their research group, or for their department or institution (n=136).

The Relevance of the Nine Articles of the Agreement

The second part of the survey contained separate questions on what areas of each articles in the Agreement on Enhancing Arctic Scientific Cooperation are relevant to the respondents. For each question respondents had to choose either “yes” an article is relevant, no or N/A (don’t know/cannot address the issue). For clarity only the relevant “yes” answers are presented here in the order of the articles (Appendix 2).

Article 1 sets the terms and definitions and in relation to that it was asked how relevant the different types of scientific activities are to respondents (Figure 3). The answers show that research activities and sharing data, as well as training the next generation of researchers were most relevant. 95% of all respondents stated that participating in and doing research projects, field work and expeditions were relevant to them and 93% found sharing scientific data, ideas, results, methods, and experiences relevant. Training, courses, conferences, workshops and meetings were regarded as relevant to 89% of the respondents. The least relevant issue (69%) was Indigenous Traditional and Local Knowledge, which was defined broadly including co-production of knowledge and using participatory research methods. This shows that despite recent statements on the importance and value of including holders of Indigenous, Traditional and Local Knowledge, it is still not understood and hasn’t become a common practice (Figure 4). What is notable here is that the survey was able to attract only few Indigenous organizations and persons and thus is weak in their views.

Article 2 and 3 focused on more general topics, where article 2 is about the purpose of the Agreement. As a result, 95% of the respondents stated that purpose of the Agreement to “increase the effectiveness and efficiency in developing scientific knowledge” is relevant. This was consistently popular among respondents from the Arctic countries with 96% of them saying it was relevant, compared with 88% from respondents from non-Arctic countries. Article 3 talks about intellectual property rights and 72% noted the ensuring fair protection and allocation of right to be relevant. Additionally, in looking at the Arctic regions, the Nordic countries, North America and the Russian Federation all value article 3 at different levels (Figure 5). 83% of researchers from the Russian Federation considered it important, compared with 70% in North America and 65% in the Nordic countries. For respondents from non-Arctic countries only 58% considered article 3 relevant.

Article 4 focuses on access and entry and exit of people, equipment and materials, which all were seen as relevant, the highest one being entry and exit of people (Figure 6). This was also seen in the third part of the survey where examples of problems in getting access to another country was collected. Obtaining visas and being able to physically cross borders to do research is seen as problematic between some countries. What is notable is that only 8% of the 136 respondents stated that they have been denied access (in all formats described in the Agreement) to a country within the Arctic. When segmenting responses, respondents from countries outside of the Agreement (non-Arctic countries) were more likely to say that entry and exit in all three categories were relevant to them. It was discovered that getting access is an issue among some countries, but overall it is not a prevalent problem. Several good experiences (by 46% of the respondents) were shared in the survey.

Figure 3. The portion of respondents finding different items in Article 1 relevant. n= number of respondents per question.

Figure 4. The portion of respondents finding Indigenous and Local Knowledge relevant to their research and the Agreement. n= number of respondents per question.

Figure 5. Percentage of respondents who find Article 3 relevant, segmented by geographic region. n= number of respondents per question.

Figure 6. Percentage of those who find Article 4 relevant, segmented by Arctic and non-Arctic. n= number of respondents per question.

Figure 7. Percentage of respondents who find Article 5 relevant, segmented by geographic region. n= number of respondents per question.

Article 5 is about gaining access to research infrastructure and facilities; 82% of respondents stated that this was relevant to them. 71% stated that logistical services were relevant to them, which was a problem noted by a few researchers in the survey. 67% stated that getting access to infrastructure was relevant to them (Figure 7). There were significant differences among the regions of the Arctic (Nordic, The Russian Federation and North America). Respondents from Nordic countries considered research facilities, logistical services and research infrastructure to be more relevant than the respondents from North America or the Russian Federation.

Article 6 focuses on different research areas (Figure 8) where access to terrestrial research sites has the highest relevance, coastal sites coming second and then marine, atmosphere and transport (either marine or aviation) being the least relevant. For article 6, no significant differences among the regions existed.

Article 7 looks deeper into data access. Most relevant was access to data from partners and other countries or institutions (85% in both cases). Article 8 focuses on education where building the capacity and expertise about the Arctic is stated to be relevant by 86 of the respondents, education activities by 69% and early career development by 67%. The percentage of individuals interested in early career development was only 60%, however when answering for a research group or department 78% consider it relevant (Figure 9).

The final article, article 9, is about Indigenous, Traditional and Local Knowledge. Partnering with and involving the holders of Indigenous, Traditional, and Local Knowledge was relevant to 71% of respondents and getting access to Indigenous, Traditional and Local Knowledge to 63%. This is in-line with the answers given to Article 1. The relevance varied greatly by regions in the Arctic with 85% of North American respondents stating that Indigenous, Traditional and Local Knowledge was relevant to them (from Article 1). The percentage from the Nordic countries was 70% and 59% from Russian respondents. Figure 10 also shows the regional variance among questions posed in article 9. This is reflective of the laws surrounding the incorporation of Indigenous, Traditional and Local Knowledge in each of the regions.

Figure 7. The portion of respondents finding different items from articles 4 and 5 relevant. n= number of respondents per question.

Figure 8. The portion of respondents finding different items from article 6 relevant. n= number of respondents per question.

Figure 9. Percentage of respondents who think different areas from articles 8 and 9 are relevant.
n = number of respondents per question.

Figure 10. Percentage of respondents who find article 9 relevant, segmented by geographic region.
n = number of respondents per question.

Experiences from Cross Border Research Collaboration

The third part of the survey collected experiences of both bad and good examples in getting access in any form to the other Arctic countries.

Experiences of Denied Access

Of the 136 respondents, only 8% said they had been declined access in one of the ways outlined in the survey. Examples given by respondents included difficulty accessing workshops, meetings, and conferences, difficulty accessing data and difficulty accessing research sites. A few researchers commented that while they had not been officially declined, bureaucratic hurdles had stopped them. One researcher wrote:

“It is not the case, in my experience, that countries decline access to the Arctic, but that difficulties or silence in communications make it impractical to access some stations and field work in a normal project life.”

Respondents also cited issues accessing data and lamented the lack of open access to data across countries. Some respondents also struggled with the lack of logistical support, specifically when trying to conduct research in remote areas of the Arctic.

Some researchers struggled to obtain what they needed for their research or simply stated that they stopped trying due to prior difficulties. Others claimed they were unable to complete their projects either due to outright denial or due to bureaucratic issues.

Positive Experiences Reported

There were 64 positive experiences cited by 36 respondents. Each individual listing was counted as a single positive experience and all forms of cooperation were counted. Both the respondents and their project locations were diverse, showing an ease of travel throughout the Arctic, not just between specific countries. The positive experiences were often credited to their existing cooperation and close working relationships with the local community, for example one researcher writes.

“I have 10 years of very positive experience with access to the Russian Arctic in Yakutia. This experience is certainly to a large extent thanks to our collaborators in Yakutsk. We so far always got access and were allowed to perform all measurements we had applied permission for.”

There also seems to be positive experiences from those outside the Arctic countries, as one researcher states:

“As a social scientist from a non-Party (non-Arctic) country, my "access" and "Scientific Activities" under the purview of the Agreement are usually undertaken at or with "partner" organizations of one or more of the contracting parties, and, so far, I have not encountered any difficulties doing my research in those contracting parties that I had the chance to visit, namely Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden, and USA.”

What was also surprising was the amount of diversity in the positive experiences. Many geographic regions had strong cooperation, with multiple positive experiences cited, these include: The Russian Federation - Nordic, Canada - Nordic, USA - Nordic & The Russian Federation, Non-Arctic - North America and Nordic.

Themes arose among the positive comments written by respondents. It was clear that good partnerships and cooperation were essential to positive experiences. As one researcher wrote:

“If you have long term contacts with people in the partner region, especially in official positions, this can lead to positive experiences and makes things much easier.”

In addition, many researchers spoke of their experiences at conferences, workshops and field courses. Respondents seemed eager to develop relationships with their colleagues from around the globe. As noted above, it was clear from the responses that good partnerships were important to cross-border research.

Conclusion and Further Research

At the end of the survey, respondents were given the opportunity to leave additional comments and many left comments and suggestions regarding the implementation of the Agreement. Some stated that they have drawn away from going to certain regions of the Arctic due to issues with bureaucratic procedures, in line with what was noted in earlier questions in the survey. However, there was optimism about the potential of the Agreement and some respondents expressed their optimism and eagerness to cooperate with others. Researchers seem optimistic that the Agreement on Enhancing International Arctic Scientific Cooperation will help to address these issues and create greater opportunities.

“I am very hopeful about collaborative projects and optimistic about future greater opportunities to work both with international partners and Arctic stakeholders (indigenous organizations, local governments, businesses)”

In this section, concerns over the ethical issues of the Agreement were raised, primarily in reference to working with Indigenous groups. This is identified as an area where further research and discussions with Indigenous communities and researchers is needed. As one respondent writes:

“It would be helpful if it was easy to see a collection of all the Arctic states' ethical research requirements/guidelines, guidelines for researching with indigenous peoples, or similar, and contact/where to apply/notify.”

We have also identified themes which could be studied further and used for increasing scientific cooperation in the Arctic. Three themes emerged from the survey as areas for further study:

1. How to include Indigenous Knowledge in research
2. How to increase awareness of the Agreement and various cooperation programs
3. How to better include non-Arctic states in Arctic research

The survey unveiled some bottlenecks in Arctic Scientific research, however the results of the survey were largely positive. Still, even the few cases of denial and discouragement are cause for concern.

Going forward, the decrease in bureaucratic hurdles is imperative for increasing cross-border research in the Arctic, an area of increasing scientific, business, and political interest. This survey showed that existing partnerships and cooperation among the nations and research groups is needed for successful cross-border scientific cooperation. Some hurdles do exist, but the only way to remove those hurdles is to make sure that the content and the Agreement is known and used when problems arise.

**AGREEMENT
ON ENHANCING INTERNATIONAL ARCTIC SCIENTIFIC COOPERATION**

The Government of Canada, the Government of the Kingdom of Denmark, the Government of the Republic of Finland, the Government of Iceland, the Government of the Kingdom of Norway, the Government of the Russian Federation, the Government of the Kingdom of Sweden, and the Government of the United States of America (hereinafter referred to as the “Parties”),

Recognizing the importance of maintaining peace, stability, and constructive cooperation in the Arctic;

Recognizing the importance of the sustainable use of resources, economic development, human health, and environmental protection;

Reiterating the urgent need for increased actions to mitigate and adapt to climate change;

Emphasizing the importance of using the best available knowledge for decision-making;

Noting the importance of international scientific cooperation in that regard;

Fully taking into account the relevant provisions of the 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, in particular the provisions in Part XIII on marine scientific research as they relate to promoting and facilitating the development and conduct of marine scientific research for peaceful purposes;

Recalling the Kiruna Declaration on the occasion of the Eighth Ministerial meeting of the Arctic Council held in May 2013 and the Iqaluit Declaration on the occasion of the Ninth Ministerial meeting of the Arctic Council held in April 2015;

Recognizing the ongoing development of the International Polar Partnership Initiative as determined by the Executive Council of the World Meteorological Organization;

Recognizing the significance of the research priorities as determined by the International Conference on Arctic Research Planning;

Recognizing the efforts of the Arctic Council and its subsidiary bodies;

Recognizing the significant scientific expertise and invaluable contributions to scientific activities being made by non-Parties and specifically by the Arctic Council Permanent Participants and Arctic Council Observers;

Recognizing the substantial benefit gained from the financial and other investments by the Arctic States and other nations in the International Polar Year and its outcomes, including in particular new scientific knowledge, infrastructure and technologies for observation and analysis;

Recognizing the excellent existing scientific cooperation already under way in many organizations and initiatives, such as the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks, the International Arctic Science Committee, the University of the Arctic, the Forum of Arctic Research Operators, the International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic, the World Meteorological Organization, the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea, the Pacific Arctic Group, the Association of Polar Early Career Scientists, indigenous knowledge institutions, the International Arctic Social Sciences Association, and many others; and

Desiring to contribute to and build upon existing cooperation and make efforts to develop and expand international Arctic scientific cooperation,

Have agreed as follows:

Article 1
Terms and definitions

For the purposes of this Agreement:

“*Facilitate*” means pursuing all necessary procedures, including giving timely consideration and making decisions as expeditiously as possible;

“*Participant*” means the Parties’ scientific and technological departments and agencies, research centers, universities and colleges, and contractors, grantees and other partners acting with or on behalf of any Party or Parties, involved in Scientific Activities under this Agreement;

“*Scientific Activities*” means efforts to advance understanding of the Arctic through scientific research, monitoring and assessment. These activities may include, but are not limited to, planning and implementing scientific research projects and programs, expeditions, observations, monitoring initiatives, surveys, modelling, and assessments; training personnel; planning, organizing and executing scientific seminars, symposia, conferences, workshops, and meetings; collecting, processing, analyzing, and sharing scientific data, ideas, results, methods, experiences, and traditional and local knowledge; developing sampling methodologies and protocols; preparing publications; and developing, implementing, and using research support logistics and research infrastructure;

“*Identified Geographic Areas*” means those areas described in Annex 1.

Article 2
Purpose

The purpose of this Agreement is to enhance cooperation in Scientific Activities in order to increase effectiveness and efficiency in the development of scientific knowledge about the Arctic.

Article 3
Intellectual property and other matters

Where appropriate, cooperative activities under this Agreement shall take place pursuant to specific implementing agreements or arrangements concluded between the Parties or Participants pertaining to their activities, particularly the financing of such activities, the use of scientific and research results, facilities, and equipment, and dispute settlement. Through such specific agreements or arrangements, the Parties shall, where appropriate, ensure, either directly or through the Participants, adequate and effective protection and fair allocation of intellectual property rights, in accordance with the applicable laws, regulations, procedures, and policies as well as the international legal obligations of the Parties concerned, and address other matters that may result from activities under this Agreement.

Article 4

Entry and exit of persons, equipment, and material

Each Party shall use its best efforts to facilitate entry to, and exit from, its territory of persons, research platforms, material, samples, data, and equipment of the Participants as needed to advance the objectives of this Agreement.

Article 5

Access to research infrastructure and facilities

The Parties shall use their best efforts to facilitate access by the Participants to national civilian research infrastructure and facilities and logistical services such as transportation and storage of equipment and material for the purpose of conducting Scientific Activities in Identified Geographic Areas under this Agreement.

Article 6

Access to research areas

1. The Parties shall facilitate access by the Participants to terrestrial, coastal, atmospheric, and marine areas in the Identified Geographic Areas, consistent with international law, for the purpose of conducting Scientific Activities.
2. The Parties shall facilitate the processing of applications to conduct marine scientific research under this Agreement consistent with the 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea.
3. The Parties also shall facilitate joint Scientific Activities that require airborne scientific data collection in the Identified Geographic Areas, and that are subject to specific implementing agreements or arrangements concluded between the Parties or Participants pertaining to those activities.

Article 7

Access to data

1. The Parties shall facilitate access to scientific information in connection with Scientific Activities under this Agreement.
2. The Parties shall support full and open access to scientific metadata and shall encourage open access to scientific data and data products and published results with minimum time delay, preferably online and free of charge or at no more than the cost of reproduction and delivery.
3. The Parties shall facilitate the distribution and sharing of scientific data and metadata by, as appropriate and to the extent practicable, adhering to commonly accepted standards, formats, protocols, and reporting.

Article 8

Education, career development and training opportunities

The Parties shall promote opportunities to include students at all levels of education, and early career scientists, in the Scientific Activities conducted under this Agreement to foster future generations of researchers and to build capacity and expertise to advance knowledge about the Arctic.

Article 9
Traditional and local knowledge

1. The Parties shall encourage Participants to utilize, as appropriate, traditional and local knowledge in the planning and conduct of Scientific Activities under this Agreement.
2. The Parties shall encourage communication, as appropriate, between holders of traditional and local knowledge and Participants conducting Scientific Activities under this Agreement.
3. The Parties shall encourage holders of traditional and local knowledge, as appropriate, to participate in Scientific Activities under this Agreement.

Article 10
Laws, regulations, procedures, and policies

Activities and obligations under this Agreement shall be conducted subject to applicable international law and the applicable laws, regulations, procedures, and policies of the Parties concerned. For those Parties that have subnational governments, the applicable laws, regulations, procedures, and policies include those of their subnational governments.

Article 11
Resources

1. Unless otherwise agreed, each Party shall bear its own costs deriving from its implementation of this Agreement.
2. Implementation of this Agreement shall be subject to the availability of relevant resources.

Article 12
Review of this Agreement

1. The Parties shall meet no later than one year after the entry into force of this Agreement, as convened by the depositary, and from then on as decided by the Parties. The Parties may elect to convene such meetings in conjunction with meetings of the Arctic Council including inviting Arctic Council Permanent Participants and Arctic Council Observers to observe and provide information. Scientific cooperation activities with non-Parties related to Arctic science may be taken into account when reviewing the implementation of this Agreement.
2. At such meetings the Parties shall consider the implementation of this Agreement, including successes achieved and obstacles to implementation, as well as ways to improve the effectiveness and implementation of this Agreement.

Article 13
Authorities and contact points

Each Party shall designate a competent national authority or authorities as the responsible point of contact for this Agreement. The names of and contact information for the designated points of contact are specified in Annex 2 to this Agreement. Each Party shall promptly inform the other Parties in writing through its competent national authority or authorities and through diplomatic channels of any changes to those designations.

Article 14
Annexes

1. Annex 1 referred to in Article 1 constitutes an integral part of this Agreement and is legally binding.
2. Annex 2 referred to in Article 13 does not constitute an integral part of this Agreement and is not legally binding.
3. At meetings of the Parties referred to in Article 12, the Parties may adopt additional legally non-binding Annexes. Annex 2 referred to in Article 13 may be modified as provided in that Article.

Article 15
Settlement of disputes

The Parties shall resolve any disputes concerning the application or interpretation of this Agreement through direct negotiations.

Article 16
Relationship with other international agreements

Nothing in this Agreement shall be construed as altering the rights or obligations of any Party under other relevant international agreements or international law.

Article 17
Cooperation with non-Parties

1. The Parties may continue to enhance and facilitate cooperation with non-Parties with regard to Arctic science.
2. Parties may in their discretion undertake with non-Parties cooperation described in this Agreement and apply measures consistent with those described in this Agreement in cooperation with non-Parties.
3. Nothing in this Agreement shall affect the rights and obligations of the Parties under agreements with non-Parties, nor preclude cooperation between the Parties and non-Parties.

Article 18
Amendments to this Agreement

1. This Agreement may be amended by written agreement of all the Parties.
2. An amendment shall enter into force 30 days after the date on which the depositary has received the last written notification through diplomatic channels that the Parties have completed the internal procedures required for its entry into force.

Article 19
Provisional application, entry into force, and withdrawal

1. This Agreement may be applied provisionally by any signatory that provides a written statement to the depositary of its intention to do so. Any such signatory shall apply this Agreement provisionally in its relations with any other signatory having made the same notification from the date of its statement or from such other date as indicated in its statement.

2. This Agreement shall enter into force for a period of five years 30 days after the date of receipt by the depositary of the last written notification through diplomatic channels that the Parties have completed the internal procedures required for its entry into force.

3. This Agreement shall be automatically renewed for further periods of five years unless a Party notifies the other Parties in writing at least six months prior to the expiration of the first period of five years or any succeeding period of five years of its intent to withdraw from this Agreement, in which event this Agreement shall continue between the remaining Parties.

4. Any Party may at any time withdraw from this Agreement by sending written notification thereof to the depositary through diplomatic channels at least six months in advance, specifying the effective date of its withdrawal. Withdrawal from this Agreement shall not affect its application among the remaining Parties.

5. Withdrawal from this Agreement by a Party shall not affect the obligations of that Party with regard to activities undertaken under this Agreement where those obligations have arisen prior to the effective date of withdrawal.

Article 20
Depositary

The Government of the Kingdom of Denmark shall be the depositary for this Agreement.

DONE at Fairbanks, Alaska, United States of America this 11th day of May, 2017. This Agreement is established in a single copy in the English, French, and Russian languages, all texts being equally authentic. The working language of this Agreement shall be English, the language in which this Agreement was negotiated. The Depositary shall transmit certified copies of this Agreement to the Parties.

ANNEX 1 - Identified Geographic Areas

Identified Geographic Areas for purposes of this Agreement are described by each Party below and include areas over which a State whose government is a Party to this Agreement exercises sovereignty, sovereign rights or jurisdiction, including land and internal waters within those areas and the adjacent territorial sea, exclusive economic zone, and continental shelf, consistent with international law. Identified Geographic Areas also include areas beyond national jurisdiction in the high seas north of 62 degrees north latitude.

The Parties agree that the Identified Geographic Areas are described solely for the purposes of this Agreement. Nothing in this Agreement shall affect the existence or delineation of any maritime entitlement or the delimitation of any boundary between States in accordance with international law.

CANADA - The territories of Yukon, Northwest Territories, and Nunavut and the adjacent marine areas of Canada.

KINGDOM OF DENMARK - The territory of the Kingdom of Denmark including Greenland and the Faroes and its marine areas above the southern limit of the Greenland exclusive economic zone and the Faroese fisheries zone.

FINLAND - The territory of Finland and its marine areas.

ICELAND - The territory of Iceland and its marine areas.

NORWAY - Marine areas north of 62 degrees north latitude, and land areas north of the Arctic Circle (66.6 degrees north latitude).

RUSSIAN FEDERATION

1. Territory of the Murmansk Region;
2. Territory of the Nenets Autonomous Area;
3. Territory of the Chukchi Autonomous Area;
4. Territory of the Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Area;
5. Territory of the municipal entity "Vorkuta" (Komi Republic);
6. Territories of Allaikhov Ulus (District), Anabar National (Dolgano-Evenk) Ulus (District), Bulun Ulus (District), Nizhnekolymsk District, Ust-Yan Ulus (District) (Sakha Republic (Yakutia));
7. Territories of the Urban District of Norilsk, Taimyr Dolgan-Nenets Municipal District, Turukhan District (Krasnoyarsk Territory);
8. Territories of the municipal entities "The City of Arkhangelsk", "Mezen Municipal District", "Novaya Zemlya", "The City of Novodvinsk", "Onega Municipal District", "Primorsky Municipal District", "Severodvinsk" (Arkhangelsk region);
9. Lands and islands of the Arctic Ocean, identified in the Resolution of the Presidium of the Central Executive Committee of the USSR dated April 15, 1926 "On the announcement of lands and islands situated in the Arctic Ocean as a territory of the Union of SSR" and other legislative acts of the USSR;

as well as adjacent marine areas.

Note: Territories of the municipal entities, listed in the abovementioned items 5 – 8, identified within the borders as of April 1, 2014.

SWEDEN - The territory of Sweden and its marine areas north of 60.5 degrees north latitude.

UNITED STATES OF AMERICA - All United States territory north of the Arctic Circle and north and west of the boundary formed by the Porcupine, Yukon, and Kuskokwim Rivers; the Aleutian chain; and adjacent marine areas in the Arctic Ocean and the Beaufort, Bering, and Chukchi Seas.

ANNEX 2 - Authorities and contact points

CANADA

Polar Knowledge Canada
170 Laurier Avenue West, 2ND Floor, Suite 200, Ottawa, Ontario K1P 5V5
Telephone: +1 613 943 8605
Email: info@polar.gc.ca

Point of contact for Marine Scientific Research requests:

Global Affairs Canada
Security and Defense Relations, 125 Sussex Drive, Ottawa, Ontario K1A 0G2
Telephone: +1 343 203 3208
Email: chris.conway@international.gc.ca ; EXTOTT-IGR@international.gc.ca

KINGDOM OF DENMARK

The Ministry of Foreign Affairs
Department for Northern America and the Arctic
Asiatisk Plads 2, 1448 Copenhagen K
Telephone: + 45 33 92 00 00
Email: ana@um.dk

Danish Agency for Science and Higher Education
Bredgade 40
DK-1260 Copenhagen K
Telephone: +45 3544 6200
Email: sfu@ufm.dk

Department of Foreign Affairs
Postboks 1340, 3900 Nuuk
Telephone: +299 34 50 00
Email: nap@nanoq.gl

Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Church
Postboks 1029, 3900 Nuuk
Telephone: +299 34 50 00
Email: ikiin@nanoq.gl

Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Trade
Gongin 7, Postbox 377, 110 Tórshavn
Telephone: +298 30 66 00
Email: uvmr@uvmr.fo

Ministry of Education, Research and Culture
Hoyvíksvegur 72, Postbox 3279, 110 Tórshavn
Telephone: +298 30 65 00
Email: mmr@mmr.fo

FINLAND

Ministry of Education and Culture
P.O. Box 29, FI-00023 Government
(Visiting addresses: Meritullinkatu 10, Helsinki;
Meritullinkatu 1, Helsinki)
Telephone: +358 2953 30004 (Switchboard)
Email: kirjaamo@minedu.fi

ICELAND

Ministry of Education, Science and Culture
Sölvhólgata 4, 150 Reykjavík
Tel: +354 545 9500
Email: postur@mmr.stjr.is

The Icelandic Center for Research
Borgartún 30, 105 Reykjavík
Tel: +354 515 5800
Email: rannis@rannis.is

NORWAY

Ministry of Education and Research
P.O. Box 8119 Dep, N-0032 Oslo
Visitor address: Kirkegata 18, Oslo
Telephone: +47 22 24 90 90
Email: postmottak@kd.dep.no

The Research Council of Norway
P.O Box 564 N-1327 Lysaker
Visitor address: Drammensveien 288, Oslo
Telephone: +47 22 03 70 00
Email: post@forskningsradet.no

RUSSIAN FEDERATION

Ministry of Education and Science
Department of Science and Technology
Tverskaya st., 11, Moscow 125993
Telephone: +7 495 629 03 64
Email: D-14@mon.gov.ru

SWEDEN

Ministry of Education and Research
103 33 Stockholm
Telephone: +46 8 405 1000
Email: u.registrator@regeringskansliet.se

UNITED STATES OF AMERICA

US Arctic Research Commission
Executive Director, US Arctic Research Commission
4350 N. Fairfax Dr., Suite 510, Arlington, VA 22203
Telephone: + 1 703 525 0113
Email: info@arctic.gov

ACCORD SUR LE RENFORCEMENT DE LA COOPÉRATION SCIENTIFIQUE INTERNATIONALE DANS L'ARCTIQUE

Le Gouvernement du Canada, le Gouvernement du Royaume de Danemark, le Gouvernement de la République de Finlande, le Gouvernement de l'Islande, le Gouvernement du Royaume de Norvège, le Gouvernement de la Fédération de Russie, le Gouvernement du Royaume de Suède et le Gouvernement des États-Unis d'Amérique (ci-après dénommés les « Parties »),

Reconnaissant l'importance de maintenir la paix, la stabilité et une coopération constructive dans l'Arctique;

Reconnaissant l'importance de l'utilisation durable des ressources, du développement économique, de la santé humaine et de la protection de l'environnement;

Réaffirmant qu'il est urgent d'intensifier les mesures prises pour atténuer le changement climatique et s'y adapter;

Soulignant l'importance de recourir aux meilleures connaissances disponibles dans la prise des décisions;

Notant l'importance de la coopération scientifique internationale à cet égard;

Tenant pleinement compte des dispositions pertinentes de la Convention des Nations Unies sur le droit de la mer de 1982, en particulier celles de la partie XIII sur la recherche scientifique marine portant sur l'encouragement et la facilitation du développement et de la conduite de la recherche scientifique marine à des fins pacifiques;

Rappelant la Déclaration de Kiruna issue de la huitième réunion ministérielle du Conseil de l'Arctique tenue en mai 2013, et la Déclaration d'Iqaluit issue de la neuvième réunion ministérielle du Conseil de l'Arctique tenue en avril 2015;

Reconnaissant les avancées continues réalisées dans le cadre de l'Initiative pour un partenariat polaire international, telle qu'elle a été définie par le Conseil exécutif de l'Organisation météorologique mondiale;

Reconnaissant l'importance des priorités de recherche telles qu'elles ont été définies par la Conférence internationale sur la planification de la recherche arctique;

Reconnaissant les efforts déployés par le Conseil de l'Arctique et ses organes subsidiaires;

Reconnaissant l'expertise scientifique considérable et les contributions précieuses aux activités scientifiques apportées par des non-Parties, plus particulièrement par les participants permanents et les observateurs auprès du Conseil de l'Arctique;

Reconnaissant les avantages substantiels procurés par les investissements financiers et autres réalisés par les États de l'Arctique et d'autres nations pendant l'Année polaire internationale, ainsi que les retombées de cette dernière, en particulier les nouvelles connaissances scientifiques, les infrastructures et les technologies en matière d'observation et d'analyse;

Reconnaissant l'excellence de la coopération scientifique qui existe déjà dans le cadre de nombreuses organisations et initiatives, comme les Réseaux d'observation permanente de l'Arctique (Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks), le Comité international des sciences de l'Arctique (International Arctic Science Committee), l'Université de l'Arctique (University of the Arctic), le Forum sur la recherche arctique (Forum of Arctic Research Operators), le Réseau mondial de recherche et de

surveillance terrestres dans l'Arctique (International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic), l'Organisation météorologique mondiale, le Conseil international pour l'exploration de la mer, le Groupe Pacifique de l'Arctique (Pacific Arctic Group), l'Association des chercheurs polaires en début de carrière (Association of Polar Early Career Scientists), les institutions du savoir autochtones, l'Association internationale des sciences sociales arctiques (International Arctic Social Sciences Association) et de nombreux autres;

Désirant apporter leur contribution à la coopération existante et s'appuyer sur cette dernière, tout en déployant des efforts pour développer et élargir la coopération scientifique internationale dans l'Arctique,

Sont convenus de ce qui suit :

Article premier ***Termes et définitions***

Pour l'application du présent accord :

« *faciliter* » signifie recourir à toutes les procédures nécessaires, y compris examiner en temps utile et prendre des décisions le plus rapidement possible;

« *participant* » signifie les ministères et organismes scientifiques et technologiques, centres de recherche, universités et collèges, entrepreneurs, titulaires de subvention et autres partenaires des Parties qui agissent de concert avec une ou plusieurs Parties, ou pour le compte de celles-ci, et qui prennent part aux activités scientifiques visées dans le présent accord;

« *activités scientifiques* » signifie les efforts destinés à faire progresser la compréhension de l'Arctique au moyen de la recherche, de la surveillance et de l'évaluation scientifiques. Ces activités peuvent comprendre, entre autres, la planification et la mise en œuvre de projets et de programmes de recherche, d'expéditions, d'observations, d'initiatives de surveillance, d'études, de modélisations et d'évaluations scientifiques; la formation du personnel; la planification, l'organisation et la tenue de séminaires, colloques, conférences, ateliers et réunions scientifiques; la collecte, le traitement, l'analyse et l'échange de données, d'idées, de résultats, de méthodes et d'expériences scientifiques et de savoirs traditionnels et locaux; l'élaboration de méthodologies et de protocoles d'échantillonnage; la préparation de publications; ainsi que l'élaboration, la mise en œuvre et l'utilisation de soutiens logistiques à la recherche et d'infrastructures de recherche;

« *zones géographiques désignées* » signifie les zones décrites à l'annexe 1.

Article 2 ***Objectif***

Le présent accord vise à renforcer la coopération dans le domaine des activités scientifiques dans le but d'accroître l'efficacité et l'efficacité du développement des connaissances scientifiques sur l'Arctique.

Article 3 ***Propriété intellectuelle et autres questions***

S'il y a lieu, les activités de coopération visées dans le présent accord se déroulent conformément aux accords ou arrangements de mise en œuvre particuliers conclus entre les Parties ou les participants relativement à leurs activités, notamment en ce qui concerne le financement de ces activités, l'utilisation des résultats, des installations et de l'équipement scientifiques et de recherche, et le règlement des différends. Au moyen

de ces accords ou arrangements particuliers, les Parties assurent, s'il y a lieu, directement ou par l'intermédiaire des participants, une protection adéquate et effective et une attribution équitable des droits de propriété intellectuelle, en conformité avec les lois, règlements, procédures et politiques applicables et les obligations juridiques internationales des Parties concernées, et règlent toute autre question découlant des activités visées dans le présent accord.

Article 4

Entrée et sortie de personnes, d'équipement et de matériel

Chaque Partie s'efforce de faciliter l'entrée sur son territoire et la sortie de son territoire des personnes, des plates-formes de recherche, de matériel, des échantillons, des données et de l'équipement des participants dans la mesure nécessaire pour faire progresser la réalisation des objectifs du présent accord.

Article 5

Accès aux infrastructures et aux installations de recherche

Les Parties s'efforcent de faciliter l'accès des participants à des infrastructures et installations de recherche civiles nationales et à des services logistiques, tels que le transport et l'entreposage d'équipement et de matériel aux fins de conduite d'activités scientifiques dans les zones géographiques désignées au titre du présent accord.

Article 6

Accès aux zones de recherche

1. Les Parties facilitent l'accès des participants aux zones terrestres, côtières, atmosphériques et marines dans les zones géographiques désignées, conformément au droit international, aux fins de conduite d'activités scientifiques.
2. Les Parties facilitent le traitement des demandes d'autorisation d'effectuer des recherches scientifiques marines au titre du présent accord conformément à la Convention des Nations Unies sur le droit de la mer de 1982.
3. Les Parties facilitent aussi les activités scientifiques communes qui nécessitent la collecte de données scientifiques aériennes dans les zones géographiques désignées, et qui font l'objet d'accords ou d'arrangements de mise en œuvre particuliers conclus entre les Parties ou les participants relativement à ces activités.

Article 7

Accès aux données

1. Les Parties facilitent l'accès aux renseignements scientifiques se rapportant aux activités scientifiques visées dans le présent accord.
2. Les Parties appuient un accès total et ouvert aux métadonnées scientifiques et encouragent un accès ouvert aux données scientifiques ainsi qu'aux produits de données et aux résultats publiés, et ce dans les meilleurs délais, de préférence en ligne et à titre gratuit, ou moyennant des frais ne dépassant pas le coût de reproduction et de livraison.
3. Les Parties facilitent la distribution et l'échange de données et de métadonnées scientifiques en se conformant, s'il y a lieu et dans la mesure du possible, aux normes, formats, protocoles et rapports généralement acceptés.

Article 8

Possibilités d'apprentissage, de développement professionnel et de formation

Les Parties favorisent l'inclusion des étudiants de tous les niveaux ainsi que des chercheurs en début de carrière dans les activités scientifiques conduites au titre du présent accord afin de contribuer à la formation des futures générations de chercheurs et à l'acquisition des capacités et de l'expertise nécessaires pour faire progresser les connaissances sur l'Arctique.

Article 9

Savoirs traditionnels et locaux

1. Les Parties encouragent les participants à utiliser, s'il y a lieu, les savoirs traditionnels et locaux dans la planification et la conduite des activités scientifiques visées dans le présent accord.
2. Les Parties encouragent, s'il y a lieu, la communication entre les détenteurs de savoirs traditionnels et locaux et les participants qui mènent des activités scientifiques visées dans le présent accord.
3. Les Parties encouragent, s'il y a lieu, les détenteurs de savoirs traditionnels et locaux à participer aux activités scientifiques visées dans le présent accord.

Article 10

Lois, règlements, procédures et politiques

Les activités et les obligations visées dans le présent accord sont exécutées dans le respect des dispositions applicables du droit international et des lois, règlements, procédures et politiques applicables des Parties concernées. Dans le cas des Parties ayant des gouvernements infranationaux, les lois, règlements, procédures et politiques applicables comprennent ceux de leurs gouvernements infranationaux.

Article 11

Ressources

1. À moins qu'il n'en soit convenu autrement, chaque Partie prend en charge ses propres coûts résultant de la mise en œuvre du présent accord.
2. La mise en œuvre du présent accord est subordonnée à la disponibilité des ressources pertinentes.

Article 12

Examen du présent accord

1. Les Parties se réunissent au plus tard un an après l'entrée en vigueur du présent accord, sur convocation du dépositaire, et ensuite selon la fréquence décidée par les Parties. Les Parties peuvent décider de convoquer ces réunions en même temps que celles du Conseil de l'Arctique, y compris inviter les participants permanents et les observateurs auprès du Conseil de l'Arctique à y assister en qualité d'observateurs et à fournir des renseignements. Les activités de coopération scientifique avec des non-Parties se rapportant aux sciences de l'Arctique peuvent être prises en compte lors de l'examen de la mise en œuvre du présent accord.
2. Pendant ces réunions, les Parties examinent la mise en œuvre du présent accord, y compris les succès obtenus et les obstacles à la mise en œuvre, ainsi que les moyens d'améliorer l'efficacité et la mise en œuvre du présent accord.

Article 13
Autorités et points de contact

Chaque Partie désigne une ou plusieurs autorités nationales compétentes comme points de contact responsables du présent accord. Les noms et les coordonnées des points de contact désignés sont précisés à l'annexe 2 du présent accord. Chaque Partie informe rapidement par écrit les autres Parties, par l'intermédiaire de sa ou ses autorités nationales compétentes et par la voie diplomatique, de toute modification apportée à ces désignations.

Article 14
Annexes

1. L'annexe 1 mentionnée à l'article premier fait partie intégrante du présent accord et est juridiquement contraignante.
2. L'annexe 2 mentionnée à l'article 13 ne fait pas partie intégrante du présent accord et n'est pas juridiquement contraignante
3. Lors des réunions des Parties mentionnées à l'article 12, les Parties peuvent adopter des annexes supplémentaires non contraignantes juridiquement. L'annexe 2 mentionnée à l'article 13 peut être modifiée conformément aux dispositions de cet article.

Article 15
Règlement de différends

Les Parties règlent au moyen de négociations directes tout différend portant sur l'application ou l'interprétation du présent accord.

Article 16
Relation avec d'autres accords internationaux

Le présent accord n'a pas pour effet de modifier les droits ou obligations qui incombent aux Parties au titre d'autres accords internationaux pertinents ou du droit international.

Article 17
Coopération avec des non-Parties

1. Les Parties peuvent continuer de renforcer et de faciliter la coopération avec des non-Parties dans le domaine des sciences de l'Arctique.
2. Les Parties peuvent, à leur discrétion, entreprendre la coopération décrite dans le présent accord avec des non-Parties, et appliquer des mesures compatibles avec celles décrites dans le présent accord en collaboration avec des non-Parties.
3. Le présent accord n'a pas pour effet d'affecter les droits et obligations des Parties au titre d'accords avec des non-Parties, ni d'empêcher la coopération entre les Parties et des non-Parties.

Article 18
Amendements au présent accord

1. Le présent accord peut être amendé par accord écrit de toutes les Parties.
2. Un amendement entre en vigueur 30 jours après la date à laquelle le dépositaire a reçu, par la voie diplomatique, la dernière notification écrite l'informant que les Parties ont accompli les formalités internes requises pour son entrée en vigueur.

Article 19
Application provisoire, entrée en vigueur et retrait

1. Le présent accord peut être appliqué à titre provisoire par tout signataire ayant communiqué au dépositaire une déclaration écrite de son intention en ce sens. Le signataire en question applique le présent accord à titre provisoire dans ses relations avec tout autre signataire ayant procédé à la même notification à compter de la date de sa déclaration ou de toute autre date indiquée dans sa déclaration.
2. Le présent accord entre en vigueur pour une durée de cinq ans 30 jours après la date de la réception par le dépositaire, par la voie diplomatique, de la dernière notification écrite l'informant que les Parties ont accompli les formalités internes requises pour son entrée en vigueur.
3. Le présent accord est reconduit automatiquement pour de nouvelles périodes de cinq ans à moins qu'une Partie ne notifie par écrit aux autres Parties, au moins six mois avant l'expiration de la première période de cinq ans ou de toute période subséquente de cinq ans, son intention de se retirer du présent accord, auquel cas le présent accord demeure en vigueur entre les autres Parties.
4. Toute Partie peut se retirer en tout temps du présent accord moyennant un préavis écrit d'au moins six mois, précisant la date de prise d'effet de son retrait, envoyé au dépositaire par la voie diplomatique. Le retrait du présent accord par une Partie n'a aucune incidence sur l'application de celui-ci à l'égard des autres Parties.
5. Le retrait du présent accord par une Partie n'a aucune incidence sur les obligations de celle-ci en ce qui concerne les activités entreprises au titre du présent accord si ces obligations sont antérieures à la date de prise d'effet du retrait.

Article 20
Dépositaire

Le Gouvernement du Royaume de Danemark est le dépositaire du présent accord.

FAIT à Fairbanks (Alaska), États-Unis d'Amérique, ce 11e jour de mai 2017. Le présent accord est rédigé en un exemplaire unique en langues française, anglaise et russe, chaque version faisant également foi. La langue de travail du présent accord est l'anglais, langue dans laquelle il a été négocié. Le dépositaire transmet des copies certifiées du présent accord aux Parties.

ANNEXE 1 – Zones géographiques désignées

Les zones géographiques désignées pour l'application du présent accord sont décrites ci-dessous par chaque Partie et comprennent les zones sur lesquelles un État dont le gouvernement est Partie au présent accord exerce sa souveraineté, ses droits souverains ou sa juridiction, y compris les terres et les eaux intérieures situées dans ces zones, ainsi que la mer territoriale, la zone économique exclusive et le plateau continental adjacents, conformément au droit international. Les zones géographiques désignées comprennent aussi les zones situées au-delà de la juridiction nationale en haute mer au nord du 62° degré de latitude nord.

Les Parties conviennent que les zones géographiques désignées sont décrites uniquement pour l'application du présent accord. Le présent accord n'a aucune incidence sur l'existence ou la délimitation de droits maritimes ou la délimitation de frontières entre États conformément au droit international.

CANADA – Les territoires du Yukon, des Territoires du Nord-Ouest et du Nunavut ainsi que les zones marines adjacentes du Canada.

ROYAUME DE DANEMARK – Le territoire du Royaume de Danemark, y compris le Groenland et les îles Féroé, et ses zones marines situées au-delà de la limite sud de la zone économique exclusive du Groenland et de la zone de pêche des îles Féroé.

FINLANDE – Le territoire de la Finlande et ses zones marines.

ISLANDE – Le territoire de l'Islande et ses zones marines.

NORVÈGE – Les zones marines au nord du 62° degré de latitude nord et les zones terrestres au nord du cercle arctique (66,6° degré de latitude nord).

FÉDÉRATION DE RUSSIE

1. Territoire de la Région de Mourmansk;
2. Territoire de l'Arrondissement autonome des Nenets;
3. Territoire de l'Arrondissement autonome des Tchouktches;
4. Territoire de l'Arrondissement autonome des Iamalo-Nenets;
5. Territoire de l'entité municipale « Vorkouta » (République des Komis);
6. Territoires de l'Ulus d'Allaikhov (District), de l'Ulus national d'Anabar (Dolgano-Evenk) (District), de l'Ulus de Bulun (District), du District de Nizhnekolymsk, de l'Ulus d'Ust-Yana (District) (République de Sakha (Yakoutie));
7. Territoires du District urbain de Norilsk, du District municipal Dolgano-Nénètse de Taïmyr et du District de Touroukhansk (Territoire de Krasnoïarsk);
8. Territoires des entités municipales « La Ville d'Arkhangelsk », « District municipal de Mezen », « Novaïa Zemlia », « La Ville de Novodvinsk », « District municipal Onega », « District municipal Primorsky », « Severodvinsk » (région d'Arkhangelsk);
9. Les terres et les îles de l'océan Arctique, désignées dans la résolution du Présidium du Comité exécutif central de l'URSS datée du 15 avril 1926 intitulée « Déclaration relative aux terres et aux îles situées dans l'océan Arctique en tant que territoire de l'URSS » et d'autres actes législatifs de l'URSS;

ainsi que les zones marines adjacentes.

Nota : Les territoires des entités municipales énumérées aux points 5 à 8 ci-dessus sont désignés sur la base des frontières au 1^{er} avril 2014.

SUÈDE – Le territoire de la Suède et ses zones marines au nord du 60,5° degré de latitude nord.

ÉTATS-UNIS D'AMÉRIQUE – Tout le territoire des États-Unis d'Amérique au nord du cercle arctique et au nord et à l'ouest de la frontière tracée par la rivière Porcupine, le fleuve Yukon et le fleuve Kuskokwim; l'Arc des Aléoutiennes; et les zones marines adjacentes situées dans l'océan Arctique et les mers de Beaufort, de Béring et des Tchouktches.

ANNEXE 2 – Autorités et points de contact

CANADA

Savoir polaire Canada

170, avenue Laurier Ouest, 2^{ème} étage, bureau 200, Ottawa, Ontario K1P 5V5

Téléphone : +1 613 943 8605

Adresse électronique : info@polar.gc.ca

Point de contact pour les demandes de recherche scientifique marine :

Affaires Mondiales Canada

Sécurité et relations de défense, 125 promenade Sussex, Ottawa, Ontario K1A 0G2

Téléphone : +1 343 203 3208

Adresse électronique : chris.conway@international.gc.ca; EXTOTT-IGR@international.gc.ca

ROYAUME DE DANEMARK

Ministère des Affaires étrangères

Département de l'Amérique du Nord et de l'Arctique

Asiatisk Plads 2

1448 Copenhague K

Téléphone : +45 33 92 00 00

Adresse électronique : ana@um.dk

Agence danoise de la Science et de l'Enseignement supérieur

Bredgade 40

DK-1260 Copenhague K

Téléphone : +45 35 44 62 00

Adresse électronique : sfu@ufm.dk

Département des Affaires étrangères

Postboks 1340, 3900 Nuuk

Téléphone : +299 34 50 00

Adresse électronique : nap@nanoq.gl

Ministère de l'Éducation, de la Culture, de la Recherche et de l'Église

Postboks 1029, 3900 Nuuk

Téléphone : +299 34 50 00

Adresse électronique : ikiin@nanoq.gl

Ministère des Affaires étrangères et du Commerce

Gongin 7, Postbox 377, 110 Tórshavn

Téléphone : +298 30 66 00

Adresse électronique : uvmr@uvmr.fo

Ministère de l'Éducation, de la Recherche et de la Culture

Hoyvíksvegur 72, Postbox 3279, 110 Tórshavn

Téléphone : +298 30 65 00

Adresse électronique : mmr@mmr.fo

FINLANDE

Ministère de l'Éducation et de la Culture

P.O. Box 29, FI-00023 Government

(adresses pour les rendez-vous: Meritullinkatu 10, Helsinki;

Meritullinkatu 1, Helsinki)

Téléphone : +358 2953 30004 (standard)

Adresse électronique : kirjaamo@minedu.fi

ISLANDE

Ministère de l'Éducation, de la Science et de la Culture
Sölvhólgsgata 4, 150 Reykjavík
Téléphone : +354 545 9500
Adresse électronique : postur@mmr.stjr.is

Centre islandais pour la recherche
Borgartún 30, 105 Reykjavík
Téléphone : +354 515 5800
Adresse électronique : rannis@rannis.is

NORVÈGE

Ministère de l'Éducation et de la Recherche
P.O. Box 8119 Dep, N-0032 Oslo
Adresse pour les rendez-vous : Kirkegata 18, Oslo
Téléphone : +47 22 24 90 90
Adresse électronique : postmottak@kd.dep.no
Conseil norvégien de la recherche
P.O Box 564 N-1327 Lysaker
Adresse pour les rendez-vous : Drammensveien 288, Oslo
Téléphone : +47 22 03 70 00
Adresse électronique : post@forskningsradet.no

FÉDÉRATION DE RUSSIE

Ministère de l'Éducation et de la Science
Département de la Science et de la Technologie
11, rue Tverskaya, Moscou 125993
Téléphone : +7 (495) 629 03 64
Adresse électronique : D-14@mon.gov.ru

SUÈDE

Ministère de l'Éducation et de la Recherche
103 33 Stockholm
Téléphone : +46 8 405 1000
Adresse électronique : u.registrator@regeringskansliet.se

ÉTATS-UNIS D'AMÉRIQUE

US Arctic Research Commission
Directeur exécutif, US Arctic Research Commission
4350 N. Fairfax Dr., Suite 510,
Arlington, VA 22203
Téléphone : + 1 703 525 0113
Adresse électronique : info@arctic.gov

СОГЛАШЕНИЕ

ПО УКРЕПЛЕНИЮ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО АРКТИЧЕСКОГО НАУЧНОГО СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА

Правительство Канады, Правительство Королевства Дания, Правительство Финляндской Республики, Правительство Исландии, Правительство Королевства Норвегия, Правительство Российской Федерации, Правительство Королевства Швеция и Правительство Соединенных Штатов Америки (именуемые в дальнейшем «Стороны»),

признавая важность сохранения мира, стабильности, а также конструктивного сотрудничества в Арктике;

признавая важность устойчивого использования ресурсов, экономического развития, здоровья человека и защиты окружающей среды;

отмечая вновь острую необходимость усиленных действий по смягчению последствий изменения климата и адаптации к ним;

выделяя важность использования для принятия решений наилучших знаний, имеющихся в распоряжении;

отмечая в связи с этим важность международного научного сотрудничества;

в полной мере учитывая соответствующие положения Конвенции Организации Объединенных Наций по морскому праву 1982 года, в частности, положения Части XIII о морских научных исследованиях, так как они относятся к поощрению и облегчению развития и проведения морских научных исследований в мирных целях;

ссылаясь на Кирунскую декларацию по итогам Восьмой Министерской встречи Арктического совета, состоявшейся в мае 2013 года, и на Икалутскую декларацию по итогам Девятой Министерской встречи Арктического совета, состоявшейся в апреле 2015 года;

признавая ведущуюся разработку Международной полярной партнерской инициативы в соответствии с решением Исполнительного комитета Всемирной метеорологической организации;

признавая значение исследовательских приоритетов, определенных Международной конференцией по планированию арктических исследований;

признавая усилия Арктического совета и его вспомогательных органов;

признавая значительные научные экспертные знания и неоценимый вклад в научную деятельность сторон, которые не являются Сторонами данного Соглашения, и, в особенности, Постоянных участников Арктического совета и Наблюдателей Арктического совета;

признавая существенную пользу, полученную от финансовых и иных инвестиций арктических государств и других стран в Международный полярный год и от его результатов, включающих, в частности, новые научные знания, инфраструктуру и технологии для наблюдений и анализа;

признавая отличное научное сотрудничество, уже осуществляющееся в рамках многих организаций и инициатив, таких как Сеть арктических опорных наблюдений, Международный арктический научный комитет, Университет Арктики, Форум арктических научно-исследовательских операторов,

Международная сеть для наземных исследований и мониторинга в Арктике, Всемирная метеорологическая организация, Международный совет по исследованию моря, Тихоокеанская арктическая группа, Ассоциация молодых полярных исследователей, учреждения, занимающиеся знаниями коренных народов, Международная арктическая ассоциация общественных наук и многие другие; а также

желая оказывать поддержку существующему сотрудничеству и наращивать его, а также предпринимать усилия для развития и расширения международного арктического научного сотрудничества,

согласились о нижеследующем:

Статья 1 **Термины и определения**

Для целей настоящего Соглашения:

«*Содействовать*» означает выполнять все необходимые процедуры, включая своевременное рассмотрение вопросов и максимально оперативное, насколько возможно, принятие решений;

«*Участник*» означает научно-технические подразделения и ведомства, исследовательские центры, университеты и колледжи, а также подрядчики, грантополучатели и другие партнеры Сторон, действующие совместно с любой Стороной или Сторонами или от их имени, задействованные в научной деятельности в рамках настоящего Соглашения;

«*Научная деятельность*» означает усилия по улучшению понимания Арктики посредством научных исследований, мониторинга и оценки. Такая деятельность может включать следующие виды деятельности, но не ограничивается ими: планирование и реализацию научно-исследовательских проектов и программ, экспедиций, наблюдений, инициатив по мониторингу, съемок, моделирования и оценок; подготовку персонала; планирование, организацию и проведение научных семинаров, симпозиумов, конференций, практикумов и встреч; сбор, обработку, анализ и обмен научными данными, идеями, результатами, методами, опытом, а также традиционными и местными знаниями; разработку методологий и протоколов отбора проб; подготовку публикаций; а также развитие, реализацию и использование логистической поддержки научно-исследовательской деятельности и исследовательской инфраструктуры;

«*Установленные географические районы*» означает районы, описанные в Приложении № 1.

Статья 2 **Цель**

Целью настоящего Соглашения является укрепление сотрудничества в области научной деятельности для повышения результативности и эффективности развития научных знаний об Арктике.

Статья 3 **Интеллектуальная собственность и другие вопросы**

В тех случаях, когда это целесообразно, совместная деятельность в рамках настоящего Соглашения осуществляется в соответствии со специальными соглашениями или договоренностями о ее реализации, заключенными между

Сторонами или Участниками и относящимися к их деятельности, в частности, к финансированию такой деятельности, использованию результатов научно-исследовательской деятельности, объектов и оборудования, а также к урегулированию споров. Посредством таких специальных соглашений или договоренностей Стороны в тех случаях, когда это целесообразно, обеспечивают, напрямую или через Участников, адекватную и эффективную охрану и справедливое распределение прав на объекты интеллектуальной собственности в соответствии с применимым законодательством, подзаконными актами, процедурами и политикой, а также международно-правовыми обязательствами соответствующих Сторон, и рассматривают другие вопросы, которые могут возникнуть в результате деятельности в рамках настоящего Соглашения.

Статья 4

Въезд-выезд лиц и ввоз-вывоз оборудования и материала

Каждая из Сторон прилагает максимальные усилия для содействия въезду и ввозу на её территорию, а также выезду и вывозу с её территории физических лиц, исследовательских платформ, материала, образцов, данных и оборудования Участников, которые требуются для достижения целей настоящего Соглашения.

Статья 5

Доступ к исследовательской инфраструктуре и на объекты

Стороны прилагают максимальные усилия для содействия предоставлению Участникам доступа к национальной гражданской исследовательской инфраструктуре и на объекты, а также к логистическим услугам, таким как транспортировка и хранение оборудования и материала с целью проведения научной деятельности в установленных географических районах в рамках настоящего Соглашения.

Статья 6

Доступ в районы проведения исследований

1. Стороны содействуют доступу Участников в наземные, прибрежные, атмосферные и морские пространства в установленных географических районах в соответствии с международным правом с целью осуществления научной деятельности.
2. Стороны содействуют рассмотрению заявок на проведение морских научных исследований в рамках настоящего Соглашения в соответствии с Конвенцией Организации Объединенных Наций по морскому праву 1982 года.
3. Стороны также содействуют совместной научной деятельности, требующей воздушного сбора научных данных в установленных географических районах и являющейся предметом специальных соглашений или договоренностей, заключенных между Сторонами или Участниками в связи с этой деятельностью.

Статья 7

Доступ к данным

1. Стороны содействуют получению доступа к научной информации, связанной с научной деятельностью в рамках настоящего Соглашения.
2. Стороны оказывают поддержку полному и открытому доступу к научным метаданным и поощряют открытый доступ к научным данным и результатам обработки данных, а также к опубликованным результатам с минимальными

сроками ожидания, предпочтительно онлайн и бесплатно, или по цене, не превышающей затраты на копирование и доставку.

3. Стороны содействуют распространению и обмену научных данных и метаданных в тех случаях, когда это целесообразно и практически осуществимо, в соответствии с общепринятыми стандартами, форматами, протоколами и процедурами отчетности.

Статья 8

Образование, развитие научной карьеры и возможности для повышения квалификации

Стороны содействуют расширению возможностей для включения студентов, получающих образование различного уровня, и молодых ученых в научную деятельность, осуществляемую в рамках настоящего Соглашения, с целью подготовки будущих поколений исследователей и повышения потенциала и компетенции для улучшения знаний об Арктике.

Статья 9

Традиционные и местные знания

1. Стороны поощряют Участников использовать в тех случаях, когда это целесообразно, традиционные и местные знания при планировании и осуществлении научной деятельности в рамках настоящего Соглашения.

2. Стороны поощряют в тех случаях, когда это целесообразно, диалог между носителями традиционных и местных знаний и Участниками, осуществляющими научную деятельность в рамках настоящего Соглашения.

3. Стороны поощряют участие носителей традиционных и местных знаний в тех случаях, когда это целесообразно, в научной деятельности в рамках настоящего Соглашения.

Статья 10

Законы, подзаконные акты, процедуры, а также политика

Деятельность и обязательства по настоящему Соглашению осуществляются в соответствии с применимыми международным правом и законами, подзаконными актами, процедурами и политикой соответствующих Сторон. Для Сторон, у которых есть региональные правительства, применимые законы, подзаконные акты, процедуры и политика включают также применимые законы, подзаконные акты, процедуры и политику их региональных правительств.

Статья 11

Ресурсы

1. Если не согласовано иное, каждая из Сторон самостоятельно несет расходы, связанные с реализацией настоящего Соглашения.

2. Реализация настоящего Соглашения зависит от наличия соответствующих ресурсов.

Статья 12

Обзор выполнения настоящего Соглашения

1. Стороны встречаются не позднее чем через год после вступления в силу настоящего Соглашения по созыву Депозитария, а в дальнейшем - по решению Сторон. Стороны могут решить созывать такие встречи в привязке к заседаниям Арктического совета, в том числе приглашая Постоянных участников и Наблюдателей Арктического совета для наблюдения и предоставления информации. Совместная научная деятельность со сторонами, которые не являются Сторонами настоящего Соглашения, относящаяся к арктической науке, может приниматься во внимание при обзоре выполнения настоящего Соглашения.

2. На этих встречах Стороны рассматривают выполнение настоящего Соглашения, включая достигнутые успехи и препятствия для его выполнения, а также способы повышения результативности и улучшения выполнения настоящего Соглашения.

Статья 13

Компетентные органы и контакты

Каждая из Сторон назначает компетентный национальный орган или органы в качестве ответственного координатора для целей настоящего Соглашения. Названия и контактная информация назначенных координаторов указаны в Приложении № 2 к настоящему Соглашению. Каждая Сторона в кратчайшие сроки информирует другие Стороны о любых изменениях в этих назначениях в письменном виде через свой компетентный национальный орган или органы и по дипломатическим каналам.

Статья 14

Приложения

1. Приложение № 1, упомянутое в Статье 1, составляет неотъемлемую часть настоящего Соглашения и имеет обязательную юридическую силу.

2. Приложение № 2, упомянутое в Статье 13, не является неотъемлемой частью настоящего Соглашения и не имеет обязательной юридической силы.

3. На встречах Сторон, упомянутых в Статье 12, Стороны могут принимать дополнительные Приложения, не имеющие обязательной юридической силы. Приложение № 2, упомянутое в Статье 13, может быть изменено в соответствии с данной статьей.

Статья 15

Урегулирование споров

Стороны разрешают любые споры относительно применения или толкования настоящего Соглашения путем прямых переговоров.

Статья 16

Отношения с другими международными соглашениями

Ничто в настоящем Соглашении не истолковывается как изменяющее права или обязательства любой Стороны по другим соответствующим международным соглашениям или международному праву.

Статья 17

Сотрудничество со сторонами, не являющимися Сторонами настоящего Соглашения

1. Стороны могут продолжать укреплять и развивать сотрудничество со сторонами, не являющимися Сторонами настоящего Соглашения, в области арктической науки.

2. Стороны могут по своему усмотрению осуществлять со сторонами, не являющимися Сторонами настоящего Соглашения, сотрудничество, указанное в настоящем Соглашении, и принимать меры, согласующиеся с мерами, указанными в настоящем Соглашении, в рамках такого сотрудничества со сторонами, не являющимися Сторонами настоящего Соглашения.

3. Ничто в настоящем Соглашении не затрагивает прав и обязательств Сторон по соглашениям со сторонами, не являющимися Сторонами настоящего Соглашения, и не препятствует сотрудничеству между Сторонами и сторонами, не являющимися Сторонами настоящего Соглашения.

Статья 18

Поправки к настоящему Соглашению

1. В настоящее Соглашение могут вноситься поправки по письменному согласию всех Сторон.

2. Поправка вступает в силу через 30 дней после даты получения Депозитарием по дипломатическим каналам последнего письменного уведомления о том, что все Стороны завершили внутригосударственные процедуры, необходимые для ее вступления в силу.

Статья 19

Временное применение, вступление в силу, а также выход из Соглашения

1. Настоящее Соглашение может временно применяться любой из подписавших Сторон, предоставившей Депозитарию письменное заявление о таком своем намерении. Любая такая подписавшая Сторона временно применяет настоящее Соглашение по отношению к любой другой подписавшей Стороне, предоставившей такое же уведомление, с даты своего заявления или с любой другой даты, указанной в ее заявлении.

2. Настоящее Соглашение заключается на 5 лет и вступает в силу через 30 дней после даты получения Депозитарием по дипломатическим каналам последнего письменного уведомления о выполнении Сторонами внутригосударственных процедур, необходимых для его вступления в силу.

3. Действие настоящего Соглашения автоматически продлевается на очередные 5-летние периоды, если только одна из Сторон письменно не уведомит остальные Стороны о своем намерении выйти из настоящего Соглашения не менее чем за шесть месяцев до истечения первоначального 5-летнего периода или любого последующего 5-летнего периода, и в этом случае настоящее Соглашение остается в силе только для остальных Сторон.

4. Любая Сторона может в любое время выйти из настоящего Соглашения, направив Депозитарию по дипломатическим каналам письменное уведомление об этом не менее чем за 6 месяцев, указав дату своего выхода. Выход из настоящего Соглашения не влияет на его применение в отношениях между остальными Сторонами.

5. Выход из настоящего Соглашения любой Стороны не затрагивает обязательств этой Стороны, относящихся к деятельности, осуществляемой в рамках настоящего Соглашения, если эти обязательства возникли до даты выхода.

Статья 20
Депозитарий

Правительство Королевства Дания является Депозитарием настоящего Соглашения.

СОВЕРШЕНО в г. Фэрбанкс (Аляска, Соединенные Штаты Америки) 11 мая 2017 года. Настоящее Соглашение составлено в одном экземпляре на английском, французском и русском языках, причем все тексты имеют одинаковую силу. Рабочим языком настоящего Соглашения является английский язык, на котором велись переговоры по настоящему Соглашению. Депозитарий направляет Сторонам заверенные копии настоящего Соглашения.

ПРИЛОЖЕНИЕ № 1 – Установленные географические районы

Установленные географические районы для целей настоящего Соглашения описаны каждой из Сторон ниже и включают районы, над которыми государство, Правительство которого является одной из Сторон настоящего Соглашения, осуществляет суверенитет, суверенные права или юрисдикцию, включая его сухопутную территорию и внутренние воды в данных районах и прилегающее территориальное море, исключительную экономическую зону, а также континентальный шельф, в соответствии с международным правом. Установленные географические районы также включают районы за пределами национальной юрисдикции в открытом море к северу от 62⁰ с.ш.

Стороны соглашаются, что установленные географические районы определены исключительно для целей настоящего Соглашения. Ничто в настоящем Соглашении не влияет на существование или определение каких-либо морских прав или делимитацию любых границ между государствами в соответствии с международным правом.

КАНАДА – территории Юкон, Северо-Западные территории и Нунавут и прилегающие морские районы Канады.

КОРОЛЕВСТВО ДАНИЯ – территория Королевства Дания, включая Гренландию и Фарерские острова, а также морские районы выше южной границы исключительной экономической зоны Гренландии и рыбопромысловой зоны Фарерских островов.

ФИНЛЯНДИЯ – территория Финляндии и ее морские районы.

ИСЛАНДИЯ – территория Исландии и ее морские районы.

НОРВЕГИЯ – морские районы к северу от 62⁰ с.ш., а также сухопутные территории к северу от Северного полярного круга (66,6⁰ с.ш.)

РОССИЙСКАЯ ФЕДЕРАЦИЯ –

1. Территория Мурманской области;
2. Территория Ненецкого автономного округа;
3. Территория Чукотского автономного округа;
4. Территория Ямало-Ненецкого автономного округа;
5. Территория муниципального образования городского округа «Воркута» (Республика Коми);
6. Территории Аллаиховского улуса (района), Анабарского национального (Долгано-Эвенкийского) улуса (района), Булунского улуса (района), Нижнеколымского района, Усть-Янского улуса (района) (Республика Саха (Якутия));
7. Территории городского округа города Норильска, Таймырского Долгано-Ненецкого муниципального района, Туруханского района (Красноярский край);
8. Территории муниципальных образований «Город Архангельск», «Мезенский муниципальный район», «Новая Земля», «Город Новодвинск», «Онежский муниципальный район», «Приморский муниципальный район», «Северодвинск» (Архангельская область);
9. Земли и острова, расположенные в Северном Ледовитом океане, указанные в Постановлении Президиума Центрального Исполнительного Комитета СССР от 15 апреля 1926 г. «Об объявлении территорией Союза ССР земель и островов, расположенных в Северном Ледовитом океане» и других актах СССР;

а также прилегающие морские районы.

Примечание. Территории муниципальных образований, названных в пунктах 5 - 8, указаны в границах по состоянию на 1 апреля 2014 г.

ШВЕЦИЯ - территория Швеции и ее морские районы к северу от 60,5⁰ с.ш.

СОЕДИНЕННЫЕ ШТАТЫ АМЕРИКИ – вся территория Соединенных Штатов к северу от Северного полярного круга и к северу и к западу от границы, образуемой реками Поркьюпайн, Юкон и Кускокуим; цепь Алеутских островов; а также прилегающие морские районы Северного Ледовитого океана и моря Бофорта, Берингова и Чукотского морей.

ПРИЛОЖЕНИЕ № 2 – Компетентные органы и контакты

КАНАДА

Агентство «Polar Knowledge Canada»
170 Laurier Avenue West, 2ND Floor, Suite 200 Ottawa, Ontario K1P 5V5
Телефон: +1 613 943 8605
Email: info@polar.gc.ca

Контакт для запросов по морским научным исследованиям:
Министерство иностранных дел Канады
Вопросы безопасности и обороны,
125 Sussex Drive, Ottawa, Ontario K1A 0G2
Телефон: +1 343 203 3208
Email: chris.conway@international.gc.ca; EXTOTT-IGR@international.gc.ca

КОРОЛЕВСТВО ДАНИЯ

Министерство иностранных дел
Департамент Северной Америки и Арктики
Asiatisk Plads 2, 1448 Copenhagen K
Телефон: + 45 33 92 00 00
E-mail: ana@um.dk

Агентство науки и высшего образования Дании
Bredgade 40
DK-1260 Copenhagen K
Телефон: + 45 35 44 62 00
Email: sfu@ufm.dk

Департамент иностранных дел
Postboks 1340, 3900 Nuuk
Телефон : +299 34 50 00
Email: nar@nanoq.gl

Министерство образования, культуры, науки и по делам церкви
Postboks 1029, 3900 Nuuk
Телефон: +299 34 50 00
Email: ikiin@nanoq.gl

Министерство иностранных дел и торговли Фарерских островов
Gongin 7, Postbox 377, 110 Tórshavn
Телефон: +298 30 66 00
Email: uvmr@uvmr.fo

Министерство образования, науки и культуры Фарерских островов
Hoувíksvegur 72, Postbox 3279, 110 Tórshavn
Телефон: +298 30 65 00
Email: mmr@mmr.fo

ФИНЛЯНДИЯ

Министерство образования и культуры
P.O. Box 29, FI-00023 Government
(Адреса для посещения:
Meritullinkatu 10, Helsinki;
Meritullinkatu 1, Helsinki)
Телефон: +358 2953 30004 (Коммутатор)
E-mail: kirjaamo@minedu.fi

ИСЛАНДИЯ

Министерство образования, науки и культуры
Sölvhólsgrata 4, 150 Reykjavík, Iceland
Телефон: +354 545 9500
Email: postur@mmr.stjr.is

Исландский научно-исследовательский центр
Borgartún 30, 105 Reykjavík
Телефон: +354-515-5800
Email: rannis@rannis.is

НОРВЕГИЯ

Министерство образования и исследований
P.O. Box 8119 Dep, N-0032 Oslo
Адрес для посещения: Kirkegata 18, Oslo
Телефон: +47 22 24 90 90
E-mail: postmottak@kd.dep.no

Научно-исследовательский совет Норвегии
P.O Box 564 N-1327 Lysaker
Адрес для посещения: Drammensveien 288, Oslo
Телефон: +47 22 03 70 00
E-mail: post@forskningsradet.no

РОССИЙСКАЯ ФЕДЕРАЦИЯ

Министерство образования и науки
Департамент науки и технологий
Тверская ул., д.11, Москва, 125993
Телефон: +7 (495) 629-03-64
E-mail: D-14@mon.gov.ru

ШВЕЦИЯ

Министерство образования и исследований
103 33 Stockholm
Телефон: +46 8 405 1000
E-mail: u.registrator@regeringskansliet.se

СОЕДИНЕННЫЕ ШТАТЫ АМЕРИКИ

Комиссия США по арктическим исследованиям
Исполнительный директор
4350 N. Fairfax Dr., Suite 510 Arlington, VA 22203
Телефон: +1-703-525-0113
Email: info@arctic.gov

For the Government of Canada
Pour le Gouvernement du Canada
За Правительство Канады

For the Government of the Kingdom of Denmark, including the Government of the
Faroe Islands and the Government of Greenland
Pour le Gouvernement du Royaume du Danemark, y compris le Gouvernement des
Îles Féroé et le Gouvernement du Groenland
За Правительство Королевства Дания, включая Правительство Фарерских
островов и Правительство Гренландии

For the Government of the Faroe Islands
Pour le Gouvernement des Îles Féroé
За Правительство Фарерских островов

For the Government of Greenland
Pour le Gouvernement du Groenland
За Правительство Гренландии

For the Government of the Republic of Finland
Pour le Gouvernement de la République de Finlande
За Правительство Финляндской Республики

For the Government of Iceland
Pour le Gouvernement de l'Islande
За Правительство Исландии

**For the Government of the Kingdom of Norway
Pour le Gouvernement du Royaume de Norvège
За Правительство Королевства Норвегия**

**For the Government of the Russian Federation
Pour le Gouvernement de la Fédération de Russie
За Правительство Российской Федерации**

**For the Government of the Kingdom of Sweden
Pour le Gouvernement du Royaume de Suède
За Правительство Королевства Швеция**

**For the Government of the United States of America
Pour le Gouvernement des États-Unis d'Amérique
За Правительство Соединенных Штатов Америки**

Potentials and expectations of the Agreement on Enhancing Arctic Scientific Cooperation

[The Agreement on Enhancing Arctic Scientific Cooperation](#) was signed in May 2017 after which it has been ratified by all Arctic eight countries (USA, Canada, Kingdom of Denmark, Iceland, Norway, Sweden, Finland and Russia). The purpose of the Agreement is to enhance cooperation in Scientific Activities in order to increase effectiveness and efficiency in the development of scientific knowledge about the Arctic. The key element of enhanced cooperation is the better access to research areas, infrastructures, facilities and data including education, training and entries and exits of the persons.

The agreement is now in force and for effective implementation it is important to know what are the needs and potential problems faced by researchers and students in getting access to Arctic (nationally and internationally).

This online survey is open to anyone who would like to contribute and its results will be shared in the above mentioned meeting. No personal data will be published or shared, only the issues provided will be presented.

The results from the survey will be analysed and a report will be compiled jointly by UArctic, IASC and IASSA to be presented at the ASSW19 in May 2019. The report will be published at the organisations website with an open access.

1. The contact information

The contact information will not be shared outside the UArctic Research Office in Oulu, Finland and is only asked in the case any follow up questions will rise. The summary of the questionnaire will be also shared among those who have given their contact information. Note, that you can also answer anomalously.

First name	<input type="text"/>
Last name	<input type="text"/>
email address	<input type="text"/>
country	<input type="text"/>
Organisation	<input type="text"/>
Department	<input type="text"/>

2. I would like to remain anonymous. For information please add the country of your residence. *

Yes

No

3. Are you answering for yourself or on behalf of department / research group or institution? *

for myself

for my research group

for department,
 institution

4. Did you know about the Agreement before entering to this survey? *

Yes

No

Question group A. A need and awareness of the agreement

This section will go over the potential of the agreement and therefore questions will focus on what parts of the agreement you envision to be relevant for you.

5. Do you know what is the geographical area of the agreement? *

Yes

No

6. Do you have partners in other country/s where you would like to have access? *

Yes

No

7. Which of the following areas of the agreement are relevant to you? The articles refer to the articles in the agreement. Please tick to the relevant boxes (N/A = difficult to assess). *

Yes No N/A

Article 1 Terms and Definitions

What type of scientific activity is relevant to you:

Research projects/programs, field work and expeditions

Observations, surveys and monitoring initiatives

Training, courses, conferences, workshops and meetings

Indigenous and local Knowledge

Sharing scientific data, ideas, results, methods and experiences

Develop methodologies and protocols, preparing publications

Organize research support logistics and research

Article 2 Purpose of the agreement

Increase effectiveness and efficiency in developing scientific knowledge

Article 3 Intellectual Property Rights:

"The agreement shall ensure fair protection and allocation of rights", is this relevant to you?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Article 4 Entry and Exit of persons, equipment, and material. Which one/s are relevant to you?			
Persons	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Equipment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Materials	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Article 5 Access to research infrastructure and facilities. Which one/s are relevant to you?			
Research facilities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Logistical services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Article 6 Access to research areas, which one/s are relevant to you?			
Terrestrial	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Coastal	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Atmosphere	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine transport / marine born instruments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Aviation transport / air borne instruments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Article 7 Access to data, which one/s are relevant to you?			
Access to data from partners	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Access to data from countries/institutions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Implementation of open access	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Article 8 Education, career development, which one/s are relevant to you?			
Education activities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Early career development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Building capacity and expertise about the Arctic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Article 9 Traditional and Local Knowledge, which one/s are relevant to you?			
Access to Traditional Knowledge/Indigenous Knowledge	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Partner with and involve holders of Indigenous, Traditional and Local Knowledge	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Question group B. Examples of problems where the agreement could be helpful in the future.

8. Have you been declined access to any Arctic countries in any of the areas included to the agreement? If yes, please specify in the following questions. *

Yes

No

9. Yes, I was declined access to research field or expedition

Please give information on the case

Coming from (which country)

Going to (what country)

10. Yes, I was declined access to observation or monitoring sites

Please give information on the case

Coming from (which country)

Going to (what country)

11. Yes, I was declined access to research facility or vessel or infrastructure

Please give information on the case

What was the country of your residence

What country operates the facility/vessel/infrastructure your access was denied

12. Yes, I was declined access to organize logistics for research or experiments

Please give information on the case

What was the country of your residence

What country declined the access?

13. Yes, I was declined access to participate training or other educational course

Please give information on the case

Coming from (which country)

Going to (what country)

14. Yes, I was declined entry visa to other country or research license

Please give information on the case

What is your nationality?

What country denied the entry or license?

15. Yes, I was declined access to participate workshop or meeting or conference

Please give information on the case

Coming from (which country)

Going to (what country)

16. Yes, I was declined access to data or results or methods and experiences

Please give information on the case

What country were you residing then?

What country denied the access?

17. Yes, I was declined the license to import or export equipment/s or sampels

Please give information on the case

Coming from (which country)

Going to (what country)

18. Any other denied access you would like to inform?

Please, give a short description here

Coming from (which country)

Going to (what country)

19. Do you have positive experiences and/or good practices in getting access to Arctic countries/region? If so, please share your experiences here

20. If you have anything else you would like to share, please add it here

